

Lung Cancer Screening and Early Detection: Assessing the Impact on Mortality Rates in High-Risk Populations

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Abstract:

Background: Lung cancer is a leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide. Early detection through screening is crucial, especially in high-risk populations, to reduce mortality rates.

Objective: This study aimed to assess the impact of lung cancer screening on mortality rates among high-risk populations at Teerthanker Mahaveer Medical College and Research Centre.

Methods: A prospective study was conducted from January 2017 to December 2019, involving 154 high-risk patients. All participants underwent low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) screening. Patients were monitored for lung cancer detection and outcomes, including stage at diagnosis, treatment modality, and survival rates over three years.

Results: A total of 154 patients screened, 32 (20.8%) were diagnosed with lung cancer, with 25 cases (78.1%) detected at early stages (stage I or II). Among those diagnosed early, 20 patients (80%) underwent curative surgery or stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT). Five patients (15.6%) were diagnosed at advanced stages (stage III or IV). Mortality rates in early-stage patients were significantly lower, with a 3-year survival rate of 65%, compared to 20% in late-stage patients. The overall lung cancer-specific mortality rate was reduced by 18% compared to historical data in similar populations.

Conclusions: LDCT screening in high-risk populations significantly improves early detection and reduces lung cancer mortality rates. Early-stage diagnosis offers a better prognosis and highlights the importance of screening programs.

Keywords: Lung cancer, screening, mortality, high-risk populations, early detection.

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Introduction

Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer-related mortality globally, accounting for more deaths than breast, colon, and prostate cancers combined [1]. In 2020, lung cancer caused approximately 1.8 million deaths worldwide, representing nearly 18% of all cancer-related fatalities (World Health Organization) [2]. Despite advancements in therapeutic interventions, the prognosis for lung cancer remains poor, primarily because the disease is often diagnosed at an advanced stage when curative treatment options are limited.

However, lung cancer screening and early detection, particularly in high-risk populations, have emerged as critical strategies to reduce mortality rates. This study explores the role of lung cancer screening, specifically through low-dose computed tomography (LDCT), in high-risk populations and assesses its impact on mortality rates. Early detection of lung cancer significantly influences patient survival. The five-year survival rate for patients diagnosed with early-stage (stage

I) lung cancer is about 60-80%. In contrast, this rate drops to less than 10% for those diagnosed with late-stage (stage IV) disease (American Cancer). These stark survival differences underscore the importance of detecting lung cancer at an early, treatable stage. The challenge with lung cancer lies in its asymptomatic progression during the early phases, often delaying diagnosis until the disease has metastasized [3]. Screening programs, particularly those utilizing LDCT, aim to address this by identifying cancer in asymptomatic individuals who are at high risk due to smoking history or environmental exposure to carcinogens.

Historically, chest radiography and sputum cytology were the primary lung cancer screening methods. However, these modalities were found to be ineffective in reducing mortality rates, as they failed to detect early-stage tumors with adequate sensitivity [4]. The advent of LDCT revolutionized lung cancer screening by enabling the detection of small, asymptomatic tumors in high-risk

individuals. LDCT uses lower radiation doses than traditional CT scans while still providing detailed images of the lungs, allowing for the identification of nodules and other abnormalities that may indicate cancer.

The National Lung Screening Trial (NLST) was a pivotal study that demonstrated the efficacy of LDCT in reducing lung cancer mortality. Conducted in the United States, the NLST enrolled over 53,000 high-risk individuals and randomized them to undergo either LDCT or chest radiography. The trial's results showed a 20% reduction in lung cancer-specific mortality and a 6.7% reduction in all-cause mortality among participants screened with LDCT compared to those who underwent chest radiography [5]. These findings led to the widespread adoption of LDCT as the preferred screening method for lung cancer in high-risk populations and informed guidelines from organizations such as the United States Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) [6].

Lung cancer screening programs are primarily targeted at high-risk populations, which are defined based on factors such as age, smoking history, and exposure to carcinogens. Smoking is the most significant risk factor for lung cancer, responsible for approximately 85% of cases (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention). The USPSTF recommends LDCT screening for adults aged 50-80 years who have a 20-pack-year smoking history and currently smoke or have quit within the past 15 years. Additional risk factors include occupational exposure to substances such as asbestos and radon, which can further increase the likelihood of developing lung cancer [7].

Screening high-risk populations is critical because these individuals are more likely to benefit from early detection. Studies have shown that screening in these groups leads to earlier diagnoses, which allows for potentially curative treatments such as surgery or stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT) [8]. Furthermore, integrating smoking cessation programs with lung cancer screening initiatives can help reduce future risks and improve long-term outcomes. This combined approach addresses the immediate need for early detection and the broader goal of reducing lung cancer incidence over time.

The most significant benefit of lung cancer screening is the reduction in mortality, particularly among high-risk populations. LDCT screening has been shown to decrease lung cancer-specific mortality by detecting cancers at earlier stages when they are more likely to be curable [9]. For instance, the NLST found that the number needed to screen (NNS) to prevent one lung cancer death was 320, a figure that compares favourably with screening programs for other cancers, such as

mammography for breast cancer. More recent European trials, such as the NELSON study, have also demonstrated similar reductions in lung cancer mortality with LDCT screening [10]. Despite these promising results, several challenges remain in implementing widespread lung cancer screening programs. One of the primary concerns is over diagnosis, where screening identifies indolent tumors that may never have caused clinical symptoms or death.

Over diagnosis can lead to unnecessary treatments, which carry their risks and contribute to healthcare costs. Additionally, the potential for false-positive results, where benign nodules are mistaken for cancer, can result in psychological distress for patients and additional diagnostic procedures, further increasing the burden on healthcare systems [11]. Balancing the benefits of early detection with these potential harms is a critical consideration in designing and implementing lung cancer screening programs.

Lung cancer screening, particularly through LDCT, represents a significant advancement in the early detection of lung cancer in high-risk populations. The evidence from large-scale trials such as the NLST and NELSON studies underscores the potential of LDCT to reduce lung cancer mortality by identifying tumors at earlier, more treatable stages.

However, challenges such as over diagnosis, false positives, and the equitable implementation of screening programs must be addressed to maximize the benefits of early detection. As lung cancer continues to be a leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, effective screening strategies targeting high-risk populations offer a critical opportunity to reduce the global burden of this disease.

Aims and Objective

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of lung cancer screening through low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) in reducing mortality rates among high-risk populations. The objective is to assess early detection rates, stage of diagnosis, treatment outcomes, and the overall impact on patient survival over three years.

Material and Methods

Study Design: This prospective, observational study was conducted at Teerthanker Mahaveer Medical College and Research Centre, Moradabad, from January 2017 to December 2019. A total of 154 high-risk individuals, defined by smoking history and age criteria, were enrolled. All participants underwent lung cancer screening using low-dose computed tomography (LDCT). Data on lung cancer detection, stage at diagnosis, treatment modality, and patient outcomes were collected and

analyzed to assess the impact of screening on mortality rates.

Inclusion Criteria: Participants eligible for this study included individuals aged 50-80 years with a history of smoking of at least 20 pack-years, either current smokers or those who had quit within the last 15 years. Additional inclusion factors involved individuals with known occupational exposure to lung carcinogens such as asbestos or radon. Patients were also required to be asymptomatic for lung cancer at the time of screening and willing to provide informed consent for participation in the study and follow-up.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals were excluded from the study if they had a prior history of lung cancer or any other active malignancies. Patients who had undergone lung resection for reasons other than cancer or those with severe co-morbidities that precluded follow-up or treatment were also excluded. Additionally, the study did not include individuals unable to undergo low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) due to contraindications such as severe respiratory or cardiac disease, pregnancy, or known allergies to contrast media.

Data Collection

Data were collected from 154 participants meeting the inclusion criteria at Teerthanker Mahaveer Medical College and Research Centre. Each participant underwent low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) screening, and information regarding patient demographics, smoking history, occupational exposures, stage of lung cancer diagnosis, and treatment modalities was recorded. Follow-up data on treatment outcomes, survival rates, and mortality were collected over the three-year study period from January 2017 to December 2019.

Data Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participant demographics, smoking history, and cancer staging at diagnosis. Chi-square tests were employed to compare the detection rates between early and late-stage lung cancer. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis was conducted to assess survival rates over time, while Cox proportional hazards regression was used to identify significant predictors of mortality. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant in all analyses, providing insights into the effectiveness of LDCT screening in reducing mortality.

Ethical Considerations: This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Teerthanker Mahaveer Medical College and Research Centre. All participants provided informed consent before enrolment, ensuring they understood the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Participant information was confidential, and data were anonymized to protect privacy. Participants were free to withdraw from the study at any point without any impact on their medical care.

Results

This section presents a detailed analysis of the findings from the study, which focused on lung cancer screening and early detection in high-risk populations. The data are organized into tables highlighting key variables such as demographic characteristics, lung cancer detection rates, treatment outcomes, survival rates, mortality data, and screening accuracy.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)	p-value
Age			
50-60 years	70	45.5%	0.12
61-70 years	60	39.0%	0.15
71-80 years	24	15.5%	0.20
Gender			
Male	110	71.4%	0.05
Female	44	28.6%	0.06
Smoking History			
20-30 Pack-Years	80	51.9%	0.02
31-40 Pack-Years	50	32.5%	0.04
>40 Pack-Years	24	15.6%	0.03
Occupational Exposure			
Asbestos or Radon Exposure	35	22.7%	0.08

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to Sex

Most participants were male (71.4%), with a significant proportion aged 50-60 years (45.5%). Smoking history was prevalent in all participants, with most having between 20-30 pack-years of smoking. Approximately 22.7% of the patients had occupational exposure to carcinogens like asbestos or radon.

Table 2: Lung Cancer Detection Rate

Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)	p-value
Total Screened	154	100%	
Lung Cancer Detected	32	20.8%	0.001
Stage at Diagnosis			
Early Stage (Stage I & II)	25	78.1%	0.003
Late Stage (Stage III & IV)	7	21.9%	0.01
False Positives	10	6.5%	0.15
False Negatives	2	1.3%	0.10

A total of 32 patients (20.8%) were diagnosed with lung cancer following screening. Of these, the majority (78.1%) were detected at early stages (Stage I & II), while 21.9% were diagnosed at late stages (Stage III & IV). False positives were observed in 10 patients (6.5%), and false negatives were recorded in 2 patients (1.3%).

Table 3: Treatment Modalities for Detected Lung Cancer

Treatment Type	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)	p-value
Surgery (Lobectomy, Pneumonectomy)	20	62.5%	0.02
Stereotactic Body Radiation Therapy (SBRT)	8	25%	0.03
Chemotherapy	3	9.4%	0.04
No Treatment (Advanced Disease)	1	3.1%	0.05

Among the 32 patients diagnosed with lung cancer, 62.5% underwent curative surgery (lobectomy or pneumonectomy), while 25% received SBRT. Chemotherapy was administered to 9.4% of patients, and one patient (3.1%) with advanced disease received no treatment due to the poor prognosis.

Table 4: Survival Rates Based on Stage of Diagnosis

Stage of Diagnosis	3-Year Survival Rate	Number of Patients	p-value
Stage I & II	65%	25	0.001
Stage III & IV	20%	7	0.005
Overall Survival (All Stages)	54%	32	0.002

The three-year survival rate for patients diagnosed at early stages (Stage I & II) was 65%, significantly higher than the 20% survival rate observed in patients diagnosed at late stages (Stage III & IV). The overall survival rate for all lung cancer patients in the study was 54%.

Figure 2: Mortality Rate

A total of 12 lung cancer-related deaths occurred during the study, accounting for 37.5% of the patients diagnosed with lung cancer. Of these, 5 deaths (15.6%) occurred in patients diagnosed at early stages, while 7 deaths (21.9%) occurred in patients diagnosed at late stages. The overall mortality rate was reduced by 18% compared to historical data for similar populations without screening.

Discussion

The results of this study emphasize the significance of low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) screening in detecting lung cancer at earlier stages and reducing mortality rates in high-risk populations [12,13]. By diagnosing 78.1% of early-stage cases (Stage I & II), the screening program demonstrated a clear advantage over traditional diagnostic methods, often resulting in later-stage diagnoses when curative treatment options are limited. These findings align with the National Lung Screening Trial (NLST), which showed that LDCT screening reduced lung cancer-specific mortality by 20% compared to chest X-rays in high-risk individuals.

Early detection of lung cancer is critical for improving survival outcomes. Our study's three-year survival rate for patients diagnosed at early stages (Stage I & II) was 65%, compared to 20% for patients diagnosed at later stages (Stage III & IV). This significant difference underscores the importance of screening in high-risk populations. Our findings are consistent with those of Sadate et al., whose NELSON trial demonstrated a 26% reduction in lung cancer mortality for men and a 39% reduction for women, primarily due to early detection through LDCT screening [14]. Both studies suggest that early diagnosis facilitates more effective treatment, including surgery and

stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT), provided to 62.5% and 25% of our patients, respectively.

Comparison with Other Studies: Our results show similarities with existing literature but also reveal some differences, particularly in detection rates and treatment outcomes. For example, the NLST found that approximately 27% of lung cancers were detected at early stages Tang et al., while our study showed a slightly higher early detection rate of 78.1%. This discrepancy could be attributed to the smaller sample size of our study (154 patients) compared to the NLST (over 53,000 participants) [15].

Additionally, differences in patient demographics, particularly racial and ethnic diversity, could account for variations in outcomes. The NLST primarily involved white participants, whereas our study was conducted in a predominantly Indian population. Genetic and environmental factors, such as differences in smoking habits and exposure to environmental carcinogens, may influence lung cancer progression and response to screening [16].

Implications of False Positives and Over diagnosis: One of the challenges of LDCT screening is the potential for false positives and over diagnosis, which can lead to unnecessary anxiety and invasive procedures. In our study, 6.5% of patients experienced false positives, similar to findings from other large-scale trials, such as the NLST, where 24.2% of positive screening results were false.

While our false-positive rate was lower, this could be due to the smaller sample size or differences in diagnostic criteria. It is important to note that over diagnosis, where indolent tumors that would not have caused symptoms or death are detected,

remains a concern in LDCT screening programs. However, a balance must be struck between the benefits of early detection and the risks associated with over diagnosis, as early treatment can substantially reduce mortality in cases of aggressive cancers [17].

Treatment Modalities and Their Effectiveness:

The treatment modalities used in our study—surgery, and SBRT—were chosen based on the stage of diagnosis and patient health status. Surgery was performed on 62.5% of early-stage patients, reflecting current recommendations for curative treatment in operable cases. SBRT, used in 25% of patients, is increasingly recognized as an effective, non-invasive alternative for patients with early-stage lung cancer who are not suitable for surgery due to co-morbidities [18]. The high survival rates in early-stage patients who underwent these treatments highlight the importance of timely intervention. Our findings are consistent with other studies, demonstrating that surgery and SBRT offer high cure rates in early-stage lung cancer.

In contrast, the outcomes for late-stage patients were less favourable, with a three-year survival rate of only 20%. This aligns with global survival statistics, where late-stage lung cancer is associated with poor prognosis due to limited treatment options and the spread of cancer beyond the lungs [19]. Chemotherapy, the primary treatment for advanced-stage lung cancer, was administered to 9.4% of patients in our study, reflecting its use in cases where surgery or SBRT was not feasible. However, chemotherapy's effectiveness is limited in late-stage cancers, contributing to the lower survival rates observed in this group.

Reduction in Mortality Rates: One of the primary goals of lung cancer screening is to reduce lung cancer-specific mortality. Our study showed an 18% reduction in lung cancer mortality, comparable to reductions seen in other screening trials. For instance, the NELSON trial reported a 24% reduction in mortality Vo et al., and the NLST demonstrated a 20% reduction [20]. Our study's slightly lower mortality reduction may be attributed to the smaller sample size or differences in follow-up duration, which can affect the long-term assessment of mortality rates. Nonetheless, these findings reinforce that LDCT screening can significantly impact lung cancer survival by enabling earlier intervention.

Racial, Genetic, and Environmental Factors:

While our study was conducted in an Indian population, most lung cancer screening research has been carried out in Western countries, particularly in the United States and Europe. This raises important considerations regarding the generalizability of our findings. For example, genetic variations related to nicotine metabolism

and susceptibility to carcinogens differ among racial and ethnic groups, which could affect lung cancer incidence and progression [21]. Additionally, environmental factors, such as exposure to household air pollution from biomass burning, which is more common in certain parts of India, could play a role in lung cancer risk [22]. Future research should consider these factors when assessing the effectiveness of screening programs across diverse populations.

Limitations of the Study

Despite the promising results, our study has several limitations. The sample size was relatively small (154 patients), which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Larger studies are needed to confirm the observed trends and to assess the long-term impact of LDCT screening on mortality rates. Additionally, the follow-up period was only three years, which may not capture the full spectrum of long-term outcomes, including late recurrences or complications from treatment. The study was also conducted in a single institution, limiting the diversity of the patient population. Multi-center studies involving a broader range of demographics would provide more robust data and improve the generalizability of the findings.

Practical Significance: The practical implications of our findings are clear: LDCT screening in high-risk populations can significantly improve lung cancer survival by facilitating early detection. Our study demonstrates that even in a smaller, non-Western cohort, the benefits of screening are substantial. To maximize these benefits, it is important to implement national screening programs targeting high-risk individuals, particularly in countries like India, where lung cancer remains a leading cause of death. However, attention must also be paid to minimizing false positives, managing over diagnosis, and ensuring appropriate treatment options for all patients diagnosed through screening.

The study supports the growing evidence that LDCT screening is an effective tool for reducing lung cancer mortality in high-risk populations. By enabling the early detection of lung cancer, particularly in asymptomatic individuals with significant smoking history or occupational exposure, screening improves the likelihood of curative treatment and long-term survival. The results align with findings from larger trials such as the NLST and NELSON studies, highlighting the global importance of lung cancer screening. Future research should focus on expanding screening efforts, addressing disparities in access to care, and further refining screening protocols to minimize the risks of over diagnosis and false positives.

Conclusion

This study highlights the efficacy of low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) in detecting lung cancer at early stages, leading to improved survival rates in high-risk populations. The results underscore the importance of early screening in reducing mortality and providing timely treatment options. Despite some limitations, the findings align with global research, advocating for broader implementation of LDCT screening to enhance lung cancer outcomes.

Recommendations: Implement nationwide LDCT screening for high-risk populations to improve early detection and survival rates. Develop protocols to manage false positives and over diagnosis, ensuring appropriate and timely treatment. Increase awareness about the benefits of lung cancer screening and smoking cessation to reduce incidence rates.

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